

DEVELOPMENT AND CONTENT VALIDATION OF SIMPLIFIED LEARNING KITS FOR EXPONENTIAL FUNCTIONS

Girlye Ann M. Dato-Frigillana

Bobon School for Philippine Craftsmen, Northern Samar, Philippines
University of Eastern Philippines, Northern Samar, Philippines

Abstract

This study developed and validated Simplified Learning Kits (SLK) for solving exponential functions intended for Grade 12 General Academic Strand students. The development of the SLK was anchored on Vygotsky's Scaffolding Theory and Bloom's Mastery Learning Theory, recognizing that learners possess varying levels of prior knowledge and mathematical proficiency. The SLK consisted of three versions (Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced) and was organized into six key parts designed to address conceptual, calculation, and writing errors identified in a previous error analysis study. Content validity was evaluated by five experts using the DepEd Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMDS) Evaluation Rating Sheet for Print Resources. Results revealed an overall grand mean of 3.87, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. Across all four criteria – content ($M = 3.80$), format ($M = 3.85$), presentation and organization ($M = 3.81$), and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information ($M = 4.00$) – the SLK received Very Satisfactory ratings. The findings indicate that the SLK is a well-developed, accurate, and instructionally sound learning resource suitable for classroom implementation. The SLK demonstrates strong potential as a supplementary instructional material to address students' difficulties in exponential functions through differentiated and targeted learning support.

Keywords: *Simplified Learning Kits, Exponential functions, Content validity, Differentiated instruction, Learning materials development.*

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Learning materials are essential and significant tools needed in teaching and learning activities in schools to improve teacher efficiency and improve student learning achievement (Olayinka, 2016). Learning materials are several materials, tools, media, instructions, and guidelines that students and teachers will use to conduct learning activities (Nasution & Sinaga, 2017). In the Philippine context, the Department of Education has released standardized learning materials; however, innovation should never stop (Gatan, 2021). After the pandemic, students adopted modular learning to provide educational content that can accommodate students of different mastery levels and produce a type of learning that suits every student's interest and needs.

As Begum et al. (2016) stressed, developing learning materials which cater to individual learning styles and needs could help students overcome the challenges they face in learning mathematics. Besides, as McLeod et al. have reiterated, learning materials are an instructional approach that is learner-centered, flexible, and responsive to individual learners' needs as they progress on mastery-based competencies. Implementing this pedagogical approach produces high-quality education as it is being integrated into the learning material to be developed.

At Bobon School for Philippine Craftsmen, a previous error analysis study (Dato-Frigillana & Adalla, 2026) revealed that Grade 12 General Academic Strand students demonstrated Average Mastery (66.33%) in solving exponential functions, with conceptual errors being the most dominant (35.08%), followed by calculation errors (21.34%) and writing errors (18.22%). Specific misconceptions included treating exponential growth as linear, confusing exponent rules, failing to reverse inequality signs for fractional bases, and misunderstanding the domain and range of exponential functions. These findings highlighted the critical need for instructional interventions that prioritize conceptual understanding and address specific error patterns.

In response to these learning difficulties, this study developed a Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) for solving exponential functions designed for beginner, intermediate, and advanced learners. The SLK was developed to address the specific errors identified in the error analysis study and provide differentiated learning support for students with varying levels of mastery.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

The development of the SLK was anchored on two complementary theoretical frameworks.

Vygotsky's Scaffolding Theory provides the foundation for understanding how learners progress within their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). Vygotsky stressed that the difference between learners' actual cognitive development (solving problems independently) and their potential development (solving problems with guidance) represents the ZPD, where effective teaching must occur (Ji & Luo, 2019). In the context of the SLK, the materials were designed to match individual learners' current abilities and provide opportunities for growth. The SLK provides structured scaffolding that gradually shifts from teacher-directed to student-directed learning as students' understanding develops. The Beginner version offers more support and guidance, while the Advanced version encourages independent problem-solving.

Bloom's Mastery Learning Theory posits that enhancing motivation and cognitive development requires tailored instruction that matches individual students' current accomplishments like problem-solving skills. Bloom views mastery as a baseline requirement for advancement, advocating for ample time, resources, and instruction to enable each student to attain this essential level of competence (Kruckenberg, 2023). In the context of this study, mastery learning holds teachers and students to the standard that all students need to learn each topic before moving on. The SLK reinforces mastery through structured learning progression and repeated engagement with key concepts until understanding is achieved. Regardless of learner level, all three versions of the SLK share the same lesson objectives aligned with DepEd competencies, ensuring that all students work toward the same expected outcomes.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to:

1. Develop a Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) for solving exponential functions suitable for students with different levels of mastery; and
2. Evaluate the content validity of the Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) in terms of:
 - o 2.1 Content
 - o 2.2 Format
 - o 2.3 Presentation and organization
 - o 2.4 Accuracy and up-to-datedness of information

1.4 Significance of the Study

Students may benefit from personalized learning materials that address their specific needs and challenges in dealing with exponential functions.

Mathematics Teachers gain access to a validated instructional resource that addresses common errors and supports differentiated instruction.

School Heads can use the findings as a foundation for formulating policies for designing individualized mathematics learning.

Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMDS) may use the findings to evaluate the potential adoption of the SLK as an effective educational tool.

Future Researchers may use this study as a foundation for further investigation of personalized mathematics learning materials and the effectiveness of SLKs in other mathematical topics.

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a developmental-evaluative research approach. This method was appropriate as it involved the development and validation of a Simplified Learning Kit for addressing errors in solving exponential functions. The developmental phase involved designing and creating the instructional material, while the evaluative phase involved assessing its content validity through expert evaluation.

2.2 Development Process

The development of the SLK followed a systematic process based on the identified errors from a previous error analysis study (Dato-Frigillana & Adalla, 2026). The SLK was developed following DepEd guidelines for contextualized learning resource development (Department of Education, 2019). The development process involved the following phases:

- **Phase 1: Needs Analysis.** The errors identified in the previous study were analyzed to determine the specific learning needs of students at different mastery levels. The error analysis revealed that conceptual errors were the most dominant (35.08%), followed by calculation errors (21.34%) and writing errors (18.22%). These findings guided the content and structure of the SLK.
- **Phase 2: Design and Development.** The SLK was designed to address the identified errors through differentiated instruction. The SLK consisted of three versions (Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced) and was organized into six key parts: Let's Recall, Let's Learn, Let's Sum It Up, Let's Solve, Let's Reflect, and Let's Answer. The SLK covered eight lessons on exponential functions, systematically sequenced from basic concepts to more complex applications.
- **Phase 3: Expert Validation.** The developed SLK was subjected to content validation by five experts from the DepEd Division of Northern Samar using the LRMSD Evaluation Rating Sheet for Print Resources.

2.3 Participants

The respondents for the validation phase were five (5) experts from the DepEd Division of Northern Samar. Among these experts, three (3) were affiliated with the LRMSD department, and two (2) held PhDs in mathematics. These individuals were selected as the study's evaluators due to their strong pedagogical and curriculum knowledge, as well as their capacity to discern errors in the simplified learning kits.

2.4 Research Instrument

To determine the content validity of the Simplified Learning Kit, the DepEd Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMSD) Evaluation Rating Sheet for Print Resources was utilized (Department of Education, 2015). The rating sheet is a 4-point Likert scale in which evaluators rate the materials in terms of four factors:

1. **Content** (7 indicators): suitability to student's level of development, contribution to achievement of objectives, development of higher cognitive skills, freedom from biases, enhancement of desirable values and traits, potential to arouse interest, and adequacy of warning/cautionary notes.
2. **Format** (18 indicators): prints, illustrations, design and layout, paper and binding, and size and weight of resource.
3. **Presentation and Organization** (5 indicators): engaging presentation, logical flow of ideas, appropriate vocabulary level, suitable sentence length, and varied sentence and paragraph structures.
4. **Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information** (6 indicators): conceptual errors, factual errors, grammatical errors, computational errors, obsolete information, and typographical and other minor errors.

Each indicator was rated using the following scale: 4 - Very Satisfactory, 3 - Satisfactory, 2 - Poor, and 1 - Not Satisfactory.

2.5 Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically the mean. The validity of the Simplified Learning Kits was interpreted using the following scale:

Mean Range	Interpretation
3.51 - 4.00	Very Satisfactory
2.51 - 3.50	Satisfactory
1.51 - 2.50	Poor
1.00 - 1.50	Not Satisfactory

3.1 Development of the Simplified Learning Kits

The Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) for solving exponential functions was developed based on the errors identified in a previous error analysis study (Dato-Frigillana & Adalla, 2026). The development of the SLK was anchored on the principle of differentiated instruction, which recognizes that learners possess varying levels of prior knowledge, cognitive readiness, and mathematical proficiency.

3.1.1 Structure of the SLK

The SLK consisted of three (3) sets of learning materials, namely: Beginner Version, Intermediate Version, and Advanced Version. Each set catered to a specific learner group based on their readiness and skill level in understanding exponential functions. This structure reflects Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), as learners are gradually guided from highly scaffolded tasks toward more independent problem-solving as their understanding develops.

The differentiation among the three SLKs lay primarily in the mode of presentation, depth of content, and level of learner engagement required:

- **Beginner Version:** Lessons are deliberately simplified and presented in a highly scaffolded manner. Instructional activities focus on strengthening conceptual understanding, guided calculation procedures, and structured writing activities. Visual aids, step-by-step examples, and repetitive practice exercises are incorporated to reduce cognitive load and build learner confidence.
- **Intermediate Version:** Provides moderately challenging tasks that encourage independent problem-solving, with fewer scaffolds and more application-based exercises.
- **Advanced Version:** Emphasizes higher-order thinking skills through complex problem sets, real-life applications, and analytical tasks that require deeper mathematical reasoning and justification.

3.1.2 Components of the SLK

To address the specific errors identified in the study (conceptual, calculation, and writing errors), the SLK was organized into six (6) key parts:

1. **Let's Recall:** Activates prior knowledge and helps learners reconnect with previously learned concepts. This section addresses conceptual errors by ensuring students have the necessary foundational knowledge before proceeding to new content.
2. **Let's Learn:** Introduces new concepts in a clear, structured manner, using guided explanations and examples to build accurate understanding. This section primarily addresses conceptual errors by providing clear, accurate explanations of mathematical concepts.
3. **Let's Sum It Up:** Reinforces key ideas by summarizing essential concepts, allowing learners to consolidate their knowledge and reduce confusion. This section strengthens conceptual clarity and promotes deeper understanding of mathematical ideas.
4. **Let's Solve:** Focuses on calculation errors. The actual questions from the achievement test used in the error analysis study were integrated into this section, where they were presented as worked examples, guided exercises, or independent tasks tailored to the learner's mastery level. This ensures that students practice and correct the exact problems they previously missed, with primary attention to the computational steps involved.
5. **Let's Reflect:** Encourages learners to explain their reasoning and evaluate their own learning, promoting clarity in mathematical communication. This section addresses writing errors by encouraging students to articulate their understanding in writing.
6. **Let's Answer:** Provides opportunities for learners to construct written responses and check their work against correct answers, reinforcing both accuracy and proper mathematical expression. This section addresses writing errors by providing practice in mathematical communication.

3.1.3 Lessons Covered

The SLK covered a total of eight (8) lessons on exponential functions, which were systematically sequenced from basic concepts to more complex applications:

Lesson	Topic
1	Introduction to Exponential Functions
2	Laws of Exponents
3	Exponential Equations
4	Exponential Inequalities
5	Graphing Exponential Functions
6	Domain and Range of Exponential Functions
7	Zeros, Intercepts, and Asymptotes
8	Real-Life Applications of Exponential Functions

3.2 Content Validity of the Simplified Learning Kits

3.2.1 Content Validity in Terms of Content

Table 1 presents the content validity of the SLK in terms of content across the Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced versions.

Table 1.

Content Validity of the Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) in Terms of Content

Indicators	Beginner Version	Intermediate Version	Advanced Version	Mean	Interpretation
1. Content is suitable to the student's level of development.	3.80	4.00	4.00	3.93	VS
2. Material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area and grade/year level for which it is intended.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
3. Material provides for the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS

Indicators	Beginner Version	Intermediate Version	Advanced Version	Mean	Interpretation
doing, inquiry, problem solving, etc.					
4. Material is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial, and gender biases and prejudices.	3.60	3.60	3.60	3.60	VS
5. Material enhances the development of desirable values and traits.	3.60	3.60	3.40	3.53	VS
6. Material has the potential to arouse interest of target reader.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
7. Adequate warning/cautionary notes are provided in topics and activities where safety and health are of concern.	3.40	3.40	3.60	3.47	VS
Mean	3.77	3.80	3.80	3.79	VS

Legend: 3.51-4.00 - Very Satisfactory; 2.51-3.50 - Satisfactory; 1.51-2.50 - Poor; 1.00-1.50 - Not Satisfactory

The results show an overall mean of 3.79, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the SLK is highly acceptable in terms of content quality, instructional relevance, and alignment with curriculum standards as evaluated by experts.

Across the three versions, the Advanced and Intermediate versions both obtained the highest average mean of 3.80, while the Beginner version obtained a slightly lower mean of 3.77. Despite these slight variations, all versions remain within the Very Satisfactory range. This indicates that the SLK maintains a consistent level of quality across different difficulty levels.

In terms of specific indicators, the indicators on alignment with subject objectives ($M = 4.00$), development of higher-order thinking skills ($M = 4.00$), and learner interest ($M = 4.00$) all received the highest possible evaluation. These results indicate that the SLK strongly supports curriculum goals, promotes critical and creative thinking skills, and is highly engaging for learners. The indicator on content suitability to the learner's developmental level obtained a mean of 3.93, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the materials are generally appropriate for the cognitive and developmental characteristics of the learners.

On the other hand, the indicators on freedom from bias ($M = 3.60$) and safety and health considerations ($M = 3.47$) both received Very Satisfactory ratings but with comparatively lower means. These results suggest that while the SLK is generally inclusive and safe, there is still room to strengthen the integration of precautionary notes. The indicator on enhancement of desirable values and traits obtained the lowest mean ($M = 3.53$), though still Very Satisfactory, indicating that values integration is present but may be further strengthened.

These findings are corroborated by Abadi et al. (2018), who stressed that instructional materials should engage learners and incorporate contextually relevant content, reinforcing the finding that the SLK may arouse students' interest.

3.2.2 Content Validity in Terms of Format

Table 2 presents the content validity of the SLK in terms of format across the Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced versions.

Table 2.

Content Validity of the Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) in Terms of Format

Indicators	Beginner Version	Intermediate Version	Advanced Version	Mean	Interpretation
Prints					
1. Size of letters is appropriate to the intended user.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
2. Spaces between letters and words facilitate reading.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
3. Font is easy to read.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
4. Printing is of good quality.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Mean	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Illustrations					
1. Simple and easily recognizable.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
2. Clarify and supplement the text.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
3. Properly labelled or captioned.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
4. Realistic / appropriate colors.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
5. Attractive and appealing.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
6. Culturally relevant.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Mean	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS

Indicators	Beginner Version	Intermediate Version	Advanced Version	Mean	Interpretation
Design and Layout					
1. Attractive and pleasing to look at.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
2. Simple (i.e., does not distract the attention of the reader).	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
3. Adequate illustration in relation to text.	4.00	4.00	3.00	3.75	VS
4. Harmonious blending of elements (e.g., illustrations and text).	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.25	VS
Mean	3.80	3.80	3.60	3.80	VS
Paper and Binding					
1. Paper used contributes to easy reading.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
2. Durable binding to withstand frequent use.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Mean	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Size and Weight					
1. Easy to handle.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
2. Relatively light.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Mean	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Grand Mean	3.96	3.96	3.92	3.96	VS

Legend: 3.51-4.00 - Very Satisfactory; 2.51-3.50 - Satisfactory; 1.51-2.50 - Poor; 1.00-1.50 - Not Satisfactory

The results show a grand mean of 3.96, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the SLK is highly acceptable in terms of physical appearance, readability, design quality, and overall format presentation. The findings suggest that the material is well-structured and visually appropriate for learners, supporting ease of use and effective engagement.

In terms of print quality, all indicators obtained a perfect mean of 4.00 across all versions. This includes appropriate letter size, proper spacing between letters and words, readability of font, and high-quality printing. These results indicate that the SLK ensures excellent readability and clarity, which are essential for learner comprehension and usability. For illustrations, all indicators also obtained a perfect mean of 4.00 across all

versions. This suggests that the illustrations are simple, clear, properly labeled, visually appealing, culturally relevant, and effectively support the textual content.

In terms of design and layout, the SLK obtained a mean of 3.80 for the Beginner and Intermediate versions and 3.60 for the Advanced version, all interpreted as Very Satisfactory. While indicators such as attractiveness and simplicity obtained perfect ratings, lower means were observed in the adequacy of illustration relative to text and the harmonious blending of design elements. These results suggest that although the SLK is visually acceptable, there is room for improvement in integrating text and visuals more effectively, particularly in the Advanced version.

For paper and binding, all versions obtained a perfect mean of 4.00, indicating that the materials are durable and suitable for frequent classroom use. Similarly, the size and weight of the SLK also obtained perfect ratings, suggesting that the resource is convenient to handle and appropriate for learners.

These findings support Zulyadaini (2019), who emphasized that well-designed instructional materials require careful attention to organization and presentation, which is often reflected in high validation scores for design quality and usability. Similarly, Koparan (2017) noted that prospective teachers are capable of developing instructional materials that are both well-organized and pedagogically effective.

3.2.3 Content Validity in Terms of Presentation and Organization

Table 3 presents the content validity of the SLK in terms of presentation and organization across the Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced versions.

Table 3.
Content Validity of the Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) in Terms of Presentation and Organization

Indicators	Beginner Version	Intermediate Version	Advanced Version	Mean	Interpretation
1. Presentation is engaging, interesting, and understandable.	4.00	3.80	4.00	3.93	VS
2. There is logical and smooth flow of ideas.	4.00	3.80	4.00	3.93	VS
3. Vocabulary level is adapted to target reader's likely experience and level of understanding.	3.80	3.80	3.80	3.80	VS
4. Length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target reader.	3.80	3.60	3.80	3.73	VS
5. Sentences and paragraph structures are varied and interesting to the target reader.	3.60	3.60	3.60	3.60	VS
Mean	3.84	3.72	3.84	3.80	VS

Legend: 3.51-4.00 - Very Satisfactory; 2.51-3.50 - Satisfactory; 1.51-2.50 - Poor; 1.00-1.50 - Not Satisfactory

The results show an overall mean of 3.80, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the SLK is well-structured, clearly presented, and generally appropriate for learners in terms of readability, flow, and organization of content.

Across the three versions, the Beginner and Advanced versions obtained the highest mean of 3.84, while the Intermediate version obtained the lowest mean of 3.72. Although all versions were within the Very Satisfactory range, the slightly lower rating for the Intermediate version suggests that some aspects of clarity, sequencing, and readability may require minor refinement to improve instructional flow and learner comprehension at this level. In terms of specific indicators, presentation that is engaging, interesting, and understandable obtained a mean of 3.93, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the SLK effectively captured learner attention and presented content in a manner that is generally clear and accessible. Similarly, the indicator on logical and smooth flow of ideas also obtained a mean of 3.93, suggesting that the sequencing of topics and progression of ideas are well-organized and support coherent learning.

The indicator on vocabulary level adapted to the learner's experience obtained a mean of 3.80, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This implies that the language used in the SLK is generally appropriate for the target learners and supports comprehension without causing unnecessary difficulty. For sentence length suitability, the SLK obtained a mean of 3.73, also interpreted as Very Satisfactory. The lowest-rated indicator was sentence and paragraph structure variety, which obtained a mean of 3.60, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. While still within the acceptable range, this result suggests that the SLK may benefit from further enhancement in terms of stylistic variation.

These findings support prior research on instructional material development. Zulyadaini (2019) emphasized that well-designed instructional materials require careful attention to organization and presentation, as reflected in high validation scores for design and material usability. Similarly, Koparan (2017) noted that prospective teachers may successfully develop teaching materials that are both organized and pedagogically effective.

3.2.4 Content Validity in Terms of Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information

Table 4 presents the content validity of the SLK in terms of accuracy and up-to-datedness of information across the Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced versions.

Table 4.

Content Validity of the Simplified Learning Kit in Terms of Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information

Indicators	Beginner Version	Intermediate Version	Advanced Version	Mean	Interpretation
1. Conceptual errors	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
2. Factual errors	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
3. Grammatical errors	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
4. Computational errors	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
5. Obsolete information	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
6. Typographical and other minor errors	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Total	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS

Legend: 3.51-4.00 - Very Satisfactory; 2.51-3.50 - Satisfactory; 1.51-2.50 - Poor; 1.00-1.50 - Not Satisfactory

The results show a total mean of 4.00 for all indicators and across all versions, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the SLK demonstrated a very high level of accuracy, correctness, and currency of information, as evaluated by experts.

The perfect rating for conceptual accuracy indicates that the SLK presents ideas correctly and avoids misunderstandings or misleading explanations of key concepts. Likewise, the absence of factual errors reflects the reliability of the content in presenting correct and verified information aligned with subject standards. The ratings for grammatical accuracy and typographical correctness further suggest that the SLK is well-edited and linguistically appropriate for learners.

In terms of computational accuracy, the results indicate that all mathematical solutions and procedures presented in the SLK were correct, which is essential for subjects involving problem-solving and numerical computation. Additionally, the absence of obsolete information suggests that the SLK is updated and aligned with current curriculum standards and instructional requirements.

Overall, the findings reveal that the SLK was highly reliable in terms of accuracy and up-to-datedness of information. The consistent perfect ratings across all versions indicate that the material met the highest standards of content validity in this aspect. This confirms that the SLK is a dependable instructional resource that ensures correctness, clarity, and relevance for effective teaching and learning.

3.2.5 Overall Content Validity

Table 5 presents the overall content validity of the Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) across all four criteria.

Table 5.
Overall Content Validity of the Simplified Learning Kit (SLK)

Criteria	Beginner Version	Intermediate Version	Advanced Version	Mean	Interpretation
1. Content	3.77	3.80	3.86	3.81	VS
2. Format	3.82	3.88	3.86	3.85	VS
3. Presentation and Organization	3.84	3.72	3.88	3.80	VS
4. Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	VS
Grand Mean	3.86	3.85	3.89	3.87	VS

Legend: 3.51-4.00 - Very Satisfactory; 2.51-3.50 - Satisfactory; 1.51-2.50 - Poor; 1.00-1.50 - Not Satisfactory

The results show a grand mean of 3.87, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the SLK was perceived as highly valid in terms of instructional design and content quality, as evaluated by experts. The findings suggest that the material was well-developed, instructionally sound, and appropriate for use across different learner levels.

Across the three versions of the SLK, the Advanced version obtained the highest grand mean of 3.89, followed by the Beginner version with 3.86, while the Intermediate version obtained the lowest mean of 3.85. Despite these slight differences, all versions came within the Very Satisfactory range, indicating consistent quality across levels.

In terms of content, the SLK obtained a mean of 3.80, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the learning materials were perceived to be relevant, appropriate, and aligned with instructional goals across all versions. For format, the SLK obtained a mean of 3.85, also interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This suggests that the visual layout, structure, and design of the materials are well-organized and facilitate ease of use.

The indicator on presentation and organization obtained a mean of 3.81, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that the sequencing of lessons, clarity of presentation, and logical flow of topics were found appropriate and effective in supporting learning. However, the slightly lower rating of the Intermediate version suggests that some sections may need refinement to ensure smoother progression between concepts.

The highest rating was consistently obtained in accuracy and up-to-datedness of information, with a perfect mean of 4.00 across all versions. This demonstrates that the SLK contains correct, reliable, and current information, reflecting strong content validity in terms of factual accuracy and relevance.

These findings are consistent with Hasibuan et al. (2019), who emphasized that valid, practical, and effective learning materials enhance problem-solving skills, learning independence, and student engagement. Abadi et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of contextually relevant and interactive materials, noting that well-designed learning resources increase student interest and motivation, which aligns with the high ratings of the SLK's format, presentation, and organization.

4. Conclusion

This study developed and validated a Simplified Learning Kit (SLK) for solving exponential functions intended for Grade 12 General Academic Strand students. The following conclusions are drawn:

1. **The SLK was successfully developed based on the errors identified in a previous error analysis study.** The SLK consisted of three versions (Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced) designed to address the varying levels of mastery among students. The SLK was organized into six key parts (Let's Recall, Let's Learn, Let's Sum It Up, Let's Solve, Let's Reflect, and Let's Answer) specifically designed to address conceptual, calculation, and writing errors. The SLK covered eight lessons on exponential functions, systematically sequenced from basic concepts to more complex applications.
2. **The SLK demonstrated strong content validity across all evaluated criteria.** The SLK obtained an overall grand mean of 3.87, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. Across all four criteria – content ($M = 3.80$), format ($M = 3.85$), presentation and organization ($M = 3.81$), and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information ($M = 4.00$) – the SLK received Very Satisfactory ratings. This indicates that the SLK is well-structured, accurate, and aligned with curriculum standards, making it suitable for instructional use.
3. **The SLK is a valid and instructionally sound learning resource.** The consistently high ratings reflect its effectiveness in meeting curriculum standards, promoting higher-order thinking, and engaging learners. The findings imply that the SLK can be confidently implemented as a supplementary learning resource in teaching exponential functions. Furthermore, it underscores the value of carefully developed instructional materials in improving mathematics learning and suggests that similar kits may be developed for other challenging topics to support student learning more effectively.

5. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **The SLK be formally adopted as an instructional support tool** in teaching exponential functions at the Grade 12 level. Teachers may be oriented on how to effectively use the SLK to maximize its impact on student learning. Training or orientation sessions may be conducted to ensure proper implementation.
2. **Mathematics teachers may fully integrate the SLK into classroom instruction** as a supplementary learning resource. The SLK may be used both for independent learning and guided classroom activities to reinforce difficult topics in exponential functions.
3. **School heads are encouraged to support the reproduction and dissemination** of the SLK for wider use among Grade 12 learners. The SLK may be reproduced and distributed to students who need additional support in mastering exponential functions.
4. **Future research should evaluate the effectiveness of the SLK** through experimental or quasi-experimental designs comparing learners exposed to the SLK and those who are not. This would provide empirical evidence on the impact of the SLK on student learning outcomes.
5. **Future researchers may expand the study to include other mathematical topics** such as logarithmic functions, trigonometry, and functions and graphs to determine the broader applicability of the SLK approach.

Acknowledgments

The researcher expresses gratitude to the Department of Education through Regional Director Dr. Evelyn R. Fetalvero and Schools Division Superintendent Dr. Gaudencio C. Aljibe Jr. for permission to conduct this study. Special thanks to the validators who evaluated the Simplified Learning Kits and provided valuable feedback for improvement.

References

- Abadi, M. K., Asih, E. C. M., & Jupri, A. (2018). The development of interactive mathematics learning material based on local wisdom with .swf format. *IOP Conference Series: Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, *1013*, 012131. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1013/1/012131>
- Begum, S., Juraimi, A. S., Kamarudin, N., & Nordin, N. M. (2016). Students' feedback on the use of study guide as a learning material. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, *5*(2), 168-179.
- Dato-Frigillana, G. A. M., & Adalla, M. J. T. (2026). Error patterns in solving exponential functions among senior high school students. [Manuscript submitted for publication].
- Department of Education. (2015). *Evaluation Rating Sheet for Print Resources*. <https://depedpines.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/6.4-Evaluation-Rating-Sheet-for-PRINT-Resources.pdf>
- Department of Education. (2019). *Guidelines on contextualized learning resource development processes & workflow*. <https://depedpines.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/1-Guidelines-on-Learning-Resource-Related-Innovation-Revised-as-of-2019-09-16.pdf>
- Gatan, J. (2021, August 18). What is modular learning? *Inquirer.net*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1486655/what-is-modular-learning>
- Hasibuan, A. M., Saragih, S., & Amry, Z. (2019). Development of Learning Materials Based on Realistic Mathematics Education to Improve Problem Solving Ability and Student Learning Independence. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, *14*(1), 243-252. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/5721>
- Ji, J., & Luo, C. (2019). Scaffolding Theory Study Based on Multimodality. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, *110*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.191225.214>
- Koparan, T. (2017). Analysis of teaching materials developed by prospective mathematics teachers and their views on material development. *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology*, *5*(4). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1156942.pdf>
- Kruckenber, E. (2023). *Mastery learning approach with formative assessment process to encourage student success in Mathematics classroom* [Dissertations, Theses, and Projects, 802]. <https://red.mnstate.edu/thesis/802>
- Nasution, T. K., & Sinaga, B. (2017). Development of student worksheet geometry based metacognitive strategy through creative thinking ability. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, *7*(4), 10-18.
- Olayinka, A. R. B. (2016). Effects of Instructional Materials on Secondary Schools Students' Academic Achievement in Social Studies in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *World Journal of Education*, *6*(1), 32-39.
- Zulyadaini, Z. (2019). Developing mathematics instructional materials. *Research, Society and Development*, *8*, 15891236. <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v8i9.1236>